

Directions to Improve the Efficiency of Government and Employment Service

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Abstract

This article determines the impact of the state employment service, the level of unemployment in the country, the level of employment, the level of unemployment and the level of employment on the national economy. Proposals have been made for the implementation of comprehensive measures to provide the right to record work experience and use benefits for business and self-employed citizens.

Keywords: labor rights, employment, Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, employment level, unemployment rate, unemployment benefits, employment system,

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Introduction

Fulfillment of tasks assigned to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan the Cabinet of Ministers decided to increase the efficiency of the ministry, improve its activities, and create additional conditions for effective control. observance of legislation on labor, employment and labor protection. The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan has unhindered access to the legislation of the State Labor Inspectorate (hereinafter - the Inspectorate) on labor, employment, labor protection, compulsory insurance of civil liability of the employer and social protection. disabled people, including social infrastructure.

In addition, decisions on compliance with the legislation on the creation of working conditions for the use of all types of transport, transport communications, public communications and information within their competence are made by state and economic bodies, local governments and other organizations, as well as and must be carried out by individuals, who are employers.

Research methods

In June this year, the Republican Scientific Center for Employment and Labor Protection of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations conducted a survey of the population in 101 cities and regions of the country using a methodology developed on the basis of recommendations of the International Labor Organization. It was attended by 490 citizens' self-government bodies, 4.9 thousand households and 25.9 thousand citizens. According to the department, quarantine measures aimed at preventing the spread of coronavirus infection during the KOVID-19 pandemic have had a significant impact on the labor market.

The research results show that the unemployment rate in the country is 13.2% of the economically active population. This figure for the same period in 2019 was 9.1%. The total number of people in need of work is 1.9 million (the unemployment rate for 16-30 year olds is 20.1%, and the unemployment rate for women is 17.4%).

According to preliminary data, the labor force increased by 0.6% compared to the same period in 2019 to 19 million people, while the number of people employed in the economy decreased by 5% or 671 thousand people compared to the same period last year. ., 12.7 million people.

The number of people employed in the formal sector of the economy amounted to 5.5 million people, which is 0.2% or 12.4 thousand people less than in the same period last year. At the same time, due to restrictive measures to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection, the number of self-employed decreased by 167.5 thousand (46.4%) compared to the same period last year, and 131.2 thousand people were paid to the unemployed. the number of officials dropped sharply due to their involvement in the work.

According to the survey, the number of people who left the country in search of work abroad amounted to 2 million people, which is 553.2 thousand less than in the same period last year, and 232.1 thousand less than in the first quarter of 2020. The number of people employed in the informal sector (excluding labor migrants abroad) decreased by 2.1% or 105.3 thousand compared to the previous year and amounted to 5.1 million people. At the same time, the number of temporary one-time and seasonal workers decreased (decreased by 108.4 thousand), employees of family enterprises and entrepreneurs without registration of labor relations (87.6 thousand), Entrepreneurs operating without registration and permits (110.6 thousand). At the same time, the number of people employed in farms and personal subsidiary plots increased by 201.1 thousand people due to an increase in the number of

people living at home during the quarantine period, and a sharp increase in the amount of subsidies from the Fund for Assistance to Employment of the Population. development of personal subsidiary plots.

The right of business entities and self-employed citizens to take into account their work experience and enjoy benefits makes it possible to reduce the share of employment in the informal sector.

The number of economically inactive population in the country increased by 4.5% compared to the corresponding period of 2019. This figure increased during the survey due to the fact that representatives of business and services have temporarily suspended their activities during the quarantine measures and prefer not to engage in other activities, intending to resume their activities after the imposition of restrictions.

In January-June 2020, in order to mitigate the negative impact of the SOVID-19 pandemic on the labor market, labor authorities provided services to 588.2 thousand (159.9 thousand under 30 and 229.4 thousand women) services to the unemployed and unemployed. In particular, 501.1 thousand people were provided with jobs through permanent employment and participation in public works, trained 15.0 thousand unemployed, from the Employment Promotion Fund 27.0 thousand unemployed received 10.1 billion soums were paid unemployment benefits.

In addition, through subsidies from the Employment Promotion Fund, 24.8 thousand people were employed in personal subsidiary plots, 15 thousand people were employed as members of agricultural, sewing and handicraft cooperatives, 3000 people were involved in entrepreneurial activities, 256 employers were employed. Financial assistance was provided to 2,300 unemployed people hired by the authorities to improve their qualifications and employment of the population in need of social protection.

In January-June, the unemployment rate was 13.2%. The number of people in need of employment increased to 1.94 million. The quarantine measures have had a significant impact on the labor market.

Results

According to preliminary data, the number of labor resources amounted to 19 142.3 thousand people, an increase of 0.7% compared to the same period in 2020. The number of employed in the economy decreased by 2.2% or 301.5 thousand people compared to the same period last year and amounted to 13 296.4 thousand people. The number of people employed in the official sector of the economy amounted to 5732.4 thousand people, which is 0.4% or 20.3 thousand people more than in the same period last year.

Information on the unemployment rate, in%

Table 1

	2018	2019	2020
The Republic of Uzbekistan	9,3	9,0	10,5
Republic of Karakalpakstan	9,5	9,1	10,5
provinces:			
Andijan	9,6	9,2	10,9
Buxoro	9,0	8,9	10,6
Jizzakh	9,4	9,2	11,0
Kashkadarya	9,7	9,3	11,1
Navoi	8,7	8,5	9,4
Namangan	9,5	9,1	10,6

Samarkand	9,7	9,3	11,0
Surkhondarya region	9,5	9,3	11,1
Syrdarya	9,6	9,3	11,0
Tashkent	9,0	8,9	10,5
Fergana	9,7	9,3	10,9
Khorezm	9,5	9,1	10,9
Tashkent city	7,9	7,4	8,0

Increase in the number of employees in the formal sector as a result of the gradual easing of restrictive measures during the pandemic, the number of legal entities employed in the economy increased by 3.6% or 174.7 thousand people, individual enterprises without legal entities - by 5% or 10.8 thousand people in addition, the number of unemployed people involved in paid public works amounted to 43.5 thousand people.

Staff composition (thousand people)

Table 2

	2018	2019	2020
Labor resources	18829,6	18949,0	19142,3
as a percentage of the resident population	57,1	56,4	55,9
including:			
able-bodied working-age population	18712,1	18857,6	19052,0
as a percentage of the resident population	56,8	56,2	55,7
as a percentage of labor resources	99,4	99,5	99,5
workers younger than working age and older	117,5	91,4	95,1
as a percentage of the resident population	0,3	0,3	0,3
as a percentage of labor resources	0,6	0,5	0,5

According to the survey, the number of people who left the country to work abroad amounted to 1,838.2 thousand people, which is 128.3 thousand or 6.3% less than in the same period of this year. The number of people employed in the informal sector (excluding labor migrants working abroad) in comparison with last year increased by 5.6% or 300.7 thousand people and amounted to 5668.9 thousand people. In 2020, 1,080,667 people applied to district and city employment centers for help in finding employment.

Distribution of labor resources by economically active and inactive population (thousand people)

Table-3

	2018	2019	2020
Total workforce	18829,6	18949,0	19142,3
City	10032,5	10052,7	
as a percentage of the total	53,3	53,1	
Village	8797,1	8896,3	

as a percentage of the total	46,7	46,9	
economically active population	14641,7	14876,4	14797,9
City	7682,0	7838,2	
as a percentage of the total	52,5	52,7	
Village	6959,7	7038,2	
as a percentage of the total	47,5	47,3	
economically inactive population	4187,9	4072,6	4344,4
City	2350,5	2214,5	
as a percentage of the total	56,1	54,4	
Village	1837,4	1858,1	
as a percentage of the total	43,9	45,6	

Of those who submitted applications, 362,874 people were employed, 571,732 people were involved in public works, 52,222 unemployed were trained and 89,651 people received unemployment benefits. In 2020, at the expense of the State Fund for Assistance to Employment of the Population, 69,970 unemployed will be allocated 173,158.3 million soums have been allocated for subsidies. In particular, 10.2 billion soums will be directed to employers to cover the costs of training, retraining and advanced training of 4,481 workers hired under the leadership of employment centers. A subsidy in soums has been allocated.

At the end of 2020, the unemployment rate in Uzbekistan amounted to 10.5%. In December 2020, the Republican Scientific Center for Employment and Labor Protection of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations conducted a social survey in 108 cities and regions of the country. 490 citizens' self-government bodies, 4.9 thousand households and 26.0 thousand citizens were interviewed.

The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations will continue to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the labor market in order to conduct a comprehensive analysis, objective and qualitative assessment of the quantity and quality of labor resources, as well as the effectiveness of measures to ensure employment and employment. Work.

Information on the level of employment, in%

Table-4

	2018	2019	2020
The Republic of Uzbekistan	67,4	68,3	66,1
Republic of Karakalpakstan	62,9	63,0	61,3
provinces:			
Andijan	69,6	70,2	67,1
Buxoro	70,7	69,3	67,8
Jizzakh	61,6	67,2	66,0
Kashkadarya	64,8	64,1	61,5

Navoi	69,2	69,5	67,6
Namangan	63,8	66,5	64,4
Samarkand	66,3	65,4	62,8
Surkhondarya region	65,2	67,2	63,6
Syrdarya	70,5	69,0	65,0
Tashkent	71,4	71,5	69,0
Fergana	66,0	67,6	64,6
Khorezm	64,6	66,2	63,5
Tashkent city	77,5	80,5	83,2

The research results show that the unemployment rate in the country is 10.5% of the economically active population. This figure is down 0.6% compared to the third quarter of this year. The number of those in need of employment amounted to 1,558.4 thousand people, the unemployment rate among young people (under 30) - 16.4%, among women - 14.1%.

In the employment system, there is an increase in the number of people employed in the formal sector of the economy, and a decrease in employment in the informal sector. In particular, the total number of people employed in the economy reached 13,408.4 thousand people, which is 1.4% more than in January-June 2018. At the same time, the number of people employed in the official sector of the economy for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan increased by 326.3 thousand people, or 6.2%, to 5 593.6 thousand people. On the contrary, the number of people employed in the informal sector decreased by 137.7 thousand, or 1.7%, to 7 814.8 thousand.

This is a direct result of informal business activity and work legalization measures. The results of the study also showed that the number of people who went abroad for the purpose of labor migration decreased by 1.9% compared to the corresponding period of 2019 - from 2,644.1 thousand to 2594.1 thousand.

Labor market indicators

Table-5

Indicators	2020 g. 1st quarter	2020 g. 2 st quarter	2020 g. 3 st quarter	2020 g. 4 st quarter
Employed population (average for the period; thousand people)				
Economically active population	14838,3	14680,7	14847,8	14797,9
of which: employed	13438,6	12736,6	13205,3	13239,6
including: by type of economic activity				
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	3498,0	3811,2	3749,1	3560,0
Industry	1787,3	1605,2	1705,4	1789,7
Building	1283,8	1110,4	1208,7	1267,8
Trade	1416,7	1137,3	1358,4	1364,4
Transport and storage	644,2	523,7	634,5	623,0
Education	1154,0	1124,9	1151,6	1160,0
Health care and social services	639,5	616,1	641,7	652,1

Other types	3015,1	2807,8	2755,9	2822,5
Government sector	2549,0	2572,6	2594,6	2497,0
Non-governmental sector	10889,6	10164,0	10610,7	10742,5
Unemployed registered with the employment office	32,1	73,2	33,7	37,1

In the Center for Assistance to Employment registered 6,491 unemployed who want to start their own business, to register as an individual entrepreneur, state registration of small businesses and micro-enterprises, entrepreneurship training and insurance policy on loans - 1.5 billion soums. Subsidy allocated in soums 1.7 billion soums were allocated to organizations that recruited more than 507 low-income people in excess of the minimum quota. A subsidy in soums has been allocated. For the installation of light greenhouses, the purchase of seeds, seedlings and irrigation equipment, 35,557 landowners have allocated 10 595 billion soums on the basis of trilateral agreements between Landscape Design Services, The Employment Promotion Center and Landowners. A subsidy in soums has been allocated.

Labor remuneration

Table-6

Indicators	2020 g. 1st quarter	2020 g. 2 st quarter	2020 g. 3 st quarter	2020 g. 4 st quarter
Average monthly salary, soums	2584908,7	2560576,2	2583135,9	2673284,5
Average monthly wages by type of economic activity				
Industry	3532618,5	3462184,5	3485596,8	3679179,6
Building	3050850,8	3023786,8	3147852,9	3311790,1
Trade	2522088,8	2447085,8	2555550,6	2766943,9
Transport and storage	3377542,6	3365582,2	3304805,8	3409753,6
Accommodation and meals	1866565,6	1639069,6	1793631,8	1839536,5
Information and communication	4169588,3	4235397,0	4306162,6	4390482,5
Financial and insurance activities	5412883,9	5487711,1	5814233,7	6270653,2
Education	2089908,4	1967186,7	1939415,6	1980329,5
Health care and social services	1811339,5	1779432,4	1799364,7	1811171,7
Arts, entertainment and recreation	2272731,1	2197992,9	2216990,2	2262525,7
Other types	2602220,1	2682130,2	2715390,5	2729630,5

According to the Chinese experience, today in 471 cooperatives of the country there are 22.9 thousand unemployed, low-income and low-income families, they are allocated a subsidy in the amount of 50.7 billion soums as a share in the authorized capital of cooperatives. In 2020, 798.7 million UAH. UZS have been allocated for grant funds.

In January-June 2020, the unemployment rate in Uzbekistan amounted to 9.1%, and for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of people employed in the official sector of the economy exceeded 300 thousand people. In June 2020, the Republican Scientific Center for Employment and Labor Protection of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations conducted a social study in 104 cities and regions of the country. 462 citizens self-governing bodies, 4880 households and 25,925 citizens took part in the survey.

Analysis of the survey results showed that the unemployment rate in relation to the economically active population was 9.1 percent, which is 0.2 percentage points lower than in the corresponding period of 2018. The highest unemployment rate was recorded in Kashkadarya, Syrdarya and Fergana regions - 9.4%, and the lowest - in Tashkent (7.7%).

The number of those in need of employment was 1,342.6 thousand. People, the unemployment rate among young people (under 30) was 15.1%, among young people 15-25 years old - 16.8%, among women - 12.7%.

**Labor resources and employment in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan
(thousand people)**

Table-7

	quantity		
	labor resources	Economically active population	Economically active population
2019			
The Republic of Uzbekistan	19142,3	14797,9	13239,6
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1069,0	781,7	699,3
provinces:			
Andijan	1752,9	1387,3	1236,7
Buxoro	1070,4	876,7	783,6
Jizzakh	774,6	598,9	533,1
Kashkadarya	1817,6	1334,2	1186,7
Navoi	556,3	446,2	404,3
Namangan	1579,5	1205,3	1078,0
Samarkand	2130,4	1585,4	1410,9
Surkhondarya region	1457,6	1104,1	982,0
Syrdarya	485,7	375,1	333,7
Tashkent	1614,9	1336,5	1195,6
Fergana	2068,5	1613,9	1438,3
Khorezm	1042,4	800,8	713,7
Tashkent city	1722,3	1351,8	1243,7
2020			
The Republic of Uzbekistan	18949	14876,4	13541,1
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1063,0	782,2	711,3

provinces:			
Andijan	1741,7	1413,9	1284,5
Buxoro	1081,0	875,4	797,1
Jizzakh	764,1	590,3	536,2
Kashkadarya	1813,8	1345,3	1220,0
Navoi	555,8	450,9	412,7
Namangan	1573,9	1214,7	1104,6
Samarkand	2117,1	1604,2	1455,8
Surkhondarya region	1456,9	1128,8	1024,2
Syrdarya	484,5	385,9	350,1
Tashkent	1607,3	1353,5	1232,9
Fergana	2052,1	1644,8	1492,6
Khorezm	1029,6	810,0	736,5
Tashkent city	1608,2	1276,5	1182,6

Over the past period, regional and city employment centers issued 2,141.8 million soums to employers and the unemployed. Sum, as a result of which 2,493 people were employed.

The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations will continue to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the labor market in order to conduct a comprehensive analysis, objective and qualitative assessment of the quantity and quality of labor resources, as well as the effectiveness of measures to ensure employment and employment. Work.

Permanent population of working age (at the end of the year, thousand people)

Table-8

	2018	2019	2020
The Republic of Uzbekistan	19791,8	19951,6	20111,5
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1127,0	1136,0	1144,9
provinces:			0,0
Andijan	1827,4	1837,7	1848,0
Bukhoro	1148,6	1153,3	1158,1
Jizzakh	795,1	803,6	812,2
Kashkadarya	1897,7	1918,4	1939,2
Navoi	592,4	595,9	599,5
Namangan	1656,0	1668,8	1681,6
Samarkand	2218,6	2237,5	2256,5
Surkhondarya region	1519,7	1536,8	1553,8
Syrdarya	505,8	510,9	515,9
Tashkent	1723,0	1729,1	1735,1
Fergana	2205,3	2218,7	2232,1
Khorezm	1108,9	1119,3	1129,7
Tashkent city	1466,3	1485,6	1504,9

The number of labor resources amounted to 18,964,000 people, an increase of 1% compared to January-June 2018. The economically active population increased by 181.5

thousand people or 1.2% compared to the same period in 2018. The number of economically inactive population was 4,213.0 (an increase of 0.1%), which is explained by an increase in the number of women on maternity leave, maternity leave or taking care of children under 2 years of age by 4.4%. It should be noted that the number of people not employed on a voluntary basis has sharply decreased from 805.6 thousand to 734 thousand (8.9%), which means an increase in labor and entrepreneurial activity of the population.

**Permanent population of working age
(at the end of the year, percentage of the total population, in percent)**

Table-9

	2018	2019	2020
The Republic of Uzbekistan	59,5	58,8	58,2
Republic of Karakalpakstan	60,3	59,8	59,5
provinces:			
Andijan	59,6	58,8	58,0
Bukhoro	60,6	59,9	59,5
Jizzakh	58,8	58,1	57,6
Kashkadarya	59,1	58,5	58,2
Navoi	60,5	59,8	59,1
Namangan	60,2	59,4	58,6
Samarkand	58,4	57,7	57,2
Surkhondarya region	59,1	58,5	58,0
Syrdarya	60,9	60,4	59,9
Tashkent	59,4	58,8	58,0
Fergana	59,9	59,1	58,4
Khorezm	60,4	60,0	59,7
Tashkent city	58,4	57,8	56,2

In January-June of this year, 404,569 people applied for help in finding employment at regional and city employment centers, including 138,173 people aged 16 to 30 years. Of those who entered, 167 713 people were employed, 139 679 participated in public works, 10 085 were sent for retraining, 31 938 received unemployment benefits.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan's economy creates about 280,000 new jobs per year. For demographic reasons, nearly 600,000 jobs need to be created every year. Consequently, the number of jobs created in the economy each year should be doubled just to hire new workers entering the labor market. Most jobs need to be created through the creation of new businesses and the further expansion of existing ones.

In this process, we would like to make the following suggestions.

1. A radical review and transparency of the activities of employment agencies in the country.
2. Improving the process of calculating employment indicators.
3. Promote employment by monthly study of the composition of unemployed citizens in makhallas.
4. Create a separate website for employment agencies and promote it among the unemployed.

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